

OPPORTUNISTIC RAINFALL SENSING: STATE OF THE ART AND PERSPECTIVES IN ITALY

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ABSTRACT

Opportunistic rainfall sensing through the wireless links deployed by telecommunications companies is an interesting use case of the concept of Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC). This paper surveys the results of the research activity on this topic in Italy. Several studies highlight that the retrieved rainfall fields and the outputs of hydrological models based on opportunistic data are comparable with the ones gathered from weather radars and rain gauges. These results together with the expected trend of wireless networks towards higher frequency bands (i.e. more sensitive to rain) may help in turning a research topic into a potential new service for network providers.

Index Terms— Opportunistic sensing, Commercial microwave links, Satellite microwave links, Passive microwave remote sensing, Rain fading.

1. INTRODUCTION

The general framework of *opportunistic integration* of communication, sensing and localization functions stands for one of the strongest pillars of the next-generation 6G standard [1, 2]. According to this astonishing paradigm shift, the key role of rainfall estimation systems (RESs) has recently moved to the concept of opportunistic RES (ORESs), with the aim of improving the accuracy of rainfall maps especially required for real-time monitoring of severe meteorological events [3, 4, 5]. In equivalent words, weather tracking based on the conventional RESs, mainly *i*) rain gauge and disdrometer networks [6], *ii*) onboard satellite meteorological radars, such as those employed in the Global Precipitation Measurement

(GPM) mission by NASA and JAXA [7], and *iii*) ground-based meteorological radars [8], is envisaged to be further enhanced by adopting the novel ORESs (as detailed in Sect. 2), i.e., *a*) commercial microwave links (CMLs) [9, 10, 11], *b*) satellite microwave links (SMLs) [12, 13, 14], and *c*) fusing data supplied by both CMLs and SMLs [15].

Motivated by the above scenario, this paper aims at giving a comprehensive overview of the state-of-the-art about the main ORESs currently working on-field in Italy, with a view towards the possible perspectives that are still under study. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Sect. 2, the concept of opportunistic rainfall sensing is first introduced and then compared with conventional, i.e., non-opportunistic, approaches. Sections 3-4 describe the major results achieved by a number of recent projects in Italy based on CMLs and SMLs, respectively, whereas some conclusions and perspectives are drawn in Sect. 5.

2. OPPORTUNISTIC RAINFALL SENSING

2.1. Rationale and overview

Just to overcome a few possible drawbacks of the conventional RESs, namely, ineffectiveness of rainfall estimation accuracy, space-time availability, and data delivery delays [14], the concept of opportunistic rainfall sensing has recently taken more and more significance. The rationale behind the ORESs relies on: *i*) exploiting the existence of radio links throughout a given area despite the fact they have been devised for other purposes, i.e., the CMLs employed as backhaul in cellular networks, fixed terrestrial networks and radio links (SMLs) between GEO satellites and fixed receiver units for direct-to-home (DTH) DVB-S/S2¹ services; *ii*) measuring

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¹Digital Video Broadcasting-Satellite.

the attenuation suffered from the transmitted signal along the radio path due to rainfall by estimating the received energy-per-symbol-to-noise density ratio E_s/N_0 , which is related to the so-called received signal level (RSL); *iii*) obtaining the estimate of both occurrence and intensity of the rainfall events through proper modeling. Interestingly, it comes out that employing the opportunistic approach reveals to be very appealing in view of several advantages [10, 11, 14]: *a*) the received signals can be acquired and processed without many restrictions; *b*) scalability is feasible to achieve higher spatial density; *c*) easy and low-cost deployment of SML receiver units.

2.2. Implementation issues

Let us focus on the CML- and SML-based ORESs. Table 1 points out the most recent and the ongoing research projects carried out in Italy, whereas Fig. 1 details the (high-level) processing structure exploited for the relevant experimental campaigns (Sects. 3-4).

The first block of Fig. 1 consists in measuring the RSL metric [11]. To this end, CML data are usually collected in (almost) real time by software platforms designed for purposes of network monitoring. Conversely, the SMLs typically adopt hardware solutions [12], such as ad-hoc receivers or SmartLNBS. The latter is an appealing low-cost, small-size, low-power device branded by Eutelsat, featuring both a DVB-S2 receiver and a transmitter unit enabling the return link (actually chosen in Tuscany campaigns).

Regardless of the received metric acquisition method, sampling the RSL values follows at a rate up of 1 sample per minute or even higher to track the evolution of the rain events with the required accuracy. Then, at the remote server, the classification of "rain"/"no rain" conditions is achieved by means of specific processing, i.e., Kalman filtering [12], or machine learning (ML) approaches [16] as those based on two years of observations in the City of Genoa made by a Smart Rainfall System (SRS) station or anything else equivalent.

The task performed by the fourth block deals with the evaluation of the signal reference level from the most recent no-rain data statistics, usually called "baseline". In the following block, the current RSL readings and the baseline are processed to infer the total attenuation experienced by the CML or by the SML downlink, based on some knowledge or hypotheses, about the channel parameters [3, 4]. In the case of SMLs, after resorting to a tropospheric model including the presence of the melting layer, the length of the wet link (i.e., the slanted radio signal path across the rain) is thus evaluated. As final steps, in the seventh and eighth blocks, combining together the estimate of the total attenuation and the wet link length, yields: *i*) the specific rain attenuation (in dB/km), and *ii*) the rainfall rate (in mm/h), upon using some empirical relationship, e.g., the well-known power law model specified in ITU-R recommendation P.838-3.

Fig. 1. ORES processing flowchart.

ORES	Project (Duration) web site	Funds	Test-Range
CML	MOPRAM (2017-20) www.mopram.org	CARIPLO	Lombardy
CML	RAINBO (2016-19) www.rainbolife.eu	LIFE	Emilia Romagna
CML	ClimaxPo (2023-26)	LIFE	Po Valley
SML	SVI.I.C.T.PRECIP. (2016-19) www.nefocast.it	Tuscany Regional Govt	Tuscany, Lazio
SML	INSIDERAIN (2021-22) www.insiderain.it	Tuscany Regional Govt	Tuscany, Lazio
SML	SCORE (2021-25) score-eu-project.eu	E.C. H2020	Tuscany (Massa)
SML	SIS.I.D.M.A. (2022-25) www.ponricerca.gov.it	PON 2014-20	Liguria (Genoa)

Table 1. Recent ORES projects carried out in Italy.

3. EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGNS USING COMMERCIAL MICROWAVE LINKS

Emilia Romagna — A CML product, obtained by the RAIN-LINK [17] software package, has been evaluated on a $5 \text{ km} \times 5 \text{ km}$ grid against the precipitation products operationally used at Arpa-SIMC, the Regional Weather Service of Emilia-Romagna, in northern Italy [9]. Hourly spatially interpolated CML rainfall maps, validated with respect to the Arpa gauge-based reference (ERG5) at gridbox scale, show similar performance (R^2 of 0.46 and CV of 0.78) to adjusted radar-based precipitation gridded products. Performance improves when basin-scale (total area 7150 km^2) total precipitation amounts are considered (Fig. 2 top panel). The dependance of the product accuracy from the link density in the gridbox is shown in Fig. 2 (bottom panel) where the main performance indicators are reported as a function of the LC parameter, defined as the sum of the link path lengths divided by the gridbox area, in km km^{-2} .

A new activity in Emilia Romagna is conducted by the Regional Agency Arpa, which, through the MODMET project, in collaboration with National Civil Protection Department, analyzes data from a network of sensors displaced over the region, with the aim of building a derived product that can be used in an operational context. The network is owned by the company Lepida S.c.p.A., that shares with Arpa constantly updated received and transmitted 1-min power data, since June 2020.

Lombardy — As a second example of CML application, we

Fig. 2. Top panel: area-averaged precipitation from radar (a), raingauge adjusted radar (b) and CML (c) as compared with ERG5 product. Bottom panel: MAE (d), CC (e) and CV (f) boxplot as a function of LC quartiles.

have considered the assimilation of precipitation estimates gathered from a dense network of CMLs and from an operational network of rain gages into a rainfall-runoff model comparing flow discharge estimations with observations [18]. The case study is Lambro’s basin, a peri-urban catchment located in Lombardy, northern Italy (Fig. 3a). A semi-distributed hydrological model has been developed [18] to simulate the flow at the hourly time scale. CML raw data are minimum and maximum values of the transmitted and received power levels collected every 15 min. The methodology for the conversion of the raw data into rainfall estimates is described in [17, 10]. The semi-distributed model requires rainfall data over each sub-basin in which the catchment is partitioned. To this aim, the inverse distance weighting method has been leveraged, both for CML and rain gauge data. In general, CML estimates and nearby rain gauge observations show a fair agreement. As an example, Fig. 3b gives the comparison for the event occurred on 14-15 July 2019, while Fig. 3c shows the cumulated precipitation at the end of the event for each sub-basin. In terms of discharge simulations, the performance of the CML-based hydrological model is comparable with the one obtained with rain gauges (Fig. 3d). Considering simulations for 12 rainfall events, the average Nash-Sutcliffe efficiencies (NSE) are 0.37, and 0.35, respectively for CML- and rain gauge-based inputs. The model performance slightly increases (average NSE equal to 0.38) when the combination of CMLs and rain gauges is considered.

4. EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGNS USING SATELLITE MICROWAVE LINKS

Liguria — In [16] the performance of rain/no-rain classifiers applied to real-time SML data were computed by ML methods using three metrics: *i*) specificity, indicating how good a classifier is in predicting non-rainy observation, *ii*) recall, telling how many rainy samples are correctly classified, and

Fig. 3. Panel (a): Partition of Lambro basin into sub-basins and position of CMLs and rain gauges; panel (b): example of cumulative rainfall time series from CML estimates and nearby rain gauges observations; panel (c): example of cumulative rain depths estimated in each sub-basin; panel (d) example of observed and simulated discharge.

iii) F1-score, representing the harmonic mean of the precision and recall. A calibrated tipping bucket rain gauge (TBRG) located below the SML path, at the University of Genoa DICCA department, was used to measure reference rainfall intensity (RI) [13]. Fig. 4c shows the results, highlighting that the neural network (NN) and random forest (RF) methods presented the best trade-off among the three metrics averaged on 18 observed days and overcome the performance of decision tree (DT) and support vector machine (KS). It is observed that if the RI reference system detected rainfall, it is a sufficient condition for rain occurrence over the SRS link, while the opposite is not true since rainfall could have occurred elsewhere over the link due to its extension. Consequently, the specificity metric, which exhibited lower values in NN with respect to RF, is less meaningful than the recall one, which presented the best value. Colli et al. (2020) [19] assessed the accuracy of 2-D RI fields reconstructed from the measurements provided by 37 SRS sensors installed in the Genoa area (16 km × 20 km) by evaluating the statistics of the relative error (e) with the reference measurements performed by the ARPAL regional network of TBRG (panel *b* of Fig. 4) and comparing them with the performance of the Regional Weather Radar (WR). The analysis showed a general agreement between the precision of the 10-min RI fields reconstructed by the WR (Fig. 4b of [19]) and the SRS products at the locations of the

TBRG stations. In case of heavy rain events, the e evaluated for the SRS products was lower than that of WR in areas that are well covered by the SRS sensor network, highlighting a stronger agreement between SRS and TBRG maps.

Fig. 4. Panel a): three SRS parabolic antennas installed in Valpolcevera (Genoa, Italy) ; panel b): percentage relative error of the precipitation measurements made by SRS against TBRG reference observations in Genoa [19]; panel c) performance metrics of different real-time rain/no rain SRS classifiers based on ML algorithms assessed in the Genoa testbed [16].

Tuscany — Several SML experimental campaigns were carried out in Tuscany from 2016 to 2023, in the framework of some of the projects listed in Table 1 [12], [14]. Receiving stations were set up in many Tuscan cities (plus a couple of them around Rome in Lazio). Each station was equipped with a 80 cm-dish and a SmartLNB device (see Fig. 5b), acting as both *i*) RSL measurement/acquisition unit, and *ii*) data logger via a satellite return link supported by Eutelsat’s EUROBUS platform. In detail, the measured RSL was the energy per symbol-to-noise density ratio (ESNDR) of a DVB-S2 signal with symbol rate 29 MBaud, QPSK modulation and code rate 4/5, which is broadcast from Eutelsat 10A satellite at 10°E , with EIRP 48 dBW, carrier frequency 11.345 GHz and linear vertical polarization. The scatter plot in Fig. 5c presents the experimental results relevant to 66 rain events in the following Tuscan cities (see the map in Fig. 5a): Florence (43.8178°N , 11.2008°E) from 01-01-2019 to 31-12-2019, Pisa (43.6863°N , 10.4314°E) from 06-12-2020 to 07-01-2021, and Massa (44.0344°N , 10.1402°E) from 06-11-2022 to 14-12-2022. Each mark represents a rain event, the shade of colour indicates the duration in minutes and the shape denotes the city. For each event, the value on the y axis represents the estimate of the cumulative rainfall in mm, while the value on the x axis represents the associated reference measure by a co-located TBRG. The performance of the

opportunistic SML technique was numerically evaluated over the whole dataset as: root-mean-square error (RMSE) 2.355 mm, normalized mean absolute error (NMAE) 28.010%, normalized bias (NB) -9.540%, correlation coefficient (CC) 0.810. As apparent, experimental results of the proposed implementation of the SML technique compare, with good agreement, with that of traditional TBRG, thus validating such an approach and demonstrating that it leads to reliable and accurate rainfall estimates.

Fig. 5. Panel a): 80 cm-parabolic antenna; panel b): SmartLNB device; panel c): test sites in Tuscany (squares); panel d): estimates of accumulated precipitation from SmartLNBS compared with reference TBRG.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

In this paper, the appealing features of opportunistic rainfall sensing methods based on terrestrial and satellite microwave links have been corroborated through innovative activities accomplished by a few Italian research institutions, so acquiring a number of notable results. From one side, the novel approach has been verified to be competitive with the conventional systems (rain gauges, satellite or ground-based weather radar). From the other one, a few perspective trends have been inferred to enhance the service delivering: *i*) integration of the conventional and opportunistic platforms to get the best from each one [9]; *ii*) coordination between different opportunistic platforms, e.g. by deploying satellite-based links to fill the gaps in spatial coverage of terrestrial links, hence boosting performance [15]; *iii*) shift of wireless networks towards the use of higher frequencies, e.g. terrestrial links moving from microwaves to mmWaves and satellite links from K_u to higher K_a and Q/V bands [20, 21]; *iv*) replacement of GEO with LEO to largely increase the available opportunistic signals, by exploiting the private SpaceX StarlinkTM, OneWeb, and Amazon KuiperTM mega-constellations [22].

6. REFERENCES

- [1] R. W. Heath et al., “An overview of signal processing techniques for joint communication and radar sensing,” *J. Sel. Topics Signal Process.*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 1295–1315, 2021.
- [2] H. Wymeersch et al., “Integration of communication and sensing in 6g: a joint industrial and academic perspective,” in *IEEE 32nd Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC)*. IEEE, Sept. 2021.
- [3] J. Ostromezky D. Cherkassky and H. Messer, “Precipitation classification using measurements from commercial microwave links,” *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 52, no. 5, pp. 2350–2356, 2014.
- [4] A. Overheem R. Uijlenhoet and H. Leijnse, “Opportunistic remote sensing of rainfall using microwave links from cellular communication networks,” *WIREs WATER*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 1295–1315, 2018.
- [5] M. Graf et al., “Rainfall estimates from opportunistic sensors in germany across spatio-temporal scales,” *Journal of Hydrology*, vol. 37, 2021.
- [6] E. Adirosi et al., “Database of the italian disdrometer network,” *Earth System Science Data*, 2022.
- [7] G. J. Huffman et al., “Global precipitation measurement (gpm): Unified precipitation estimation from space,” *Remote Sensing of Clouds and Precipitations*, pp. 175–193, 2018.
- [8] M. Neuper et al., “Quantitative precipitation estimation with weather radar using a data- and information-based approach,” *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, vol. 23, no. 9, 2019.
- [9] G. Roversi et al., “Commercial microwave links as a tool for operational rainfall monitoring in northern italy,” *Atmospheric Measurements Techniques*, vol. 13, pp. 5779–5797, 2020.
- [10] R. Nebuloni et al., “Comparison of cml rainfall data against rain gauges and disdrometers in a mountainous environment,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 9, 2022.
- [11] B. Lian et al., “A review on rainfall measurement based on commercial microwave links in wireless cellular networks,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 12, 2022.
- [12] F. Giannetti et al., “The nefocast system for detection and estimation of rainfall fields by the opportunistic use of broadcast satellite signals,” *IEEE Aerosp. Electron Syst. Mag.*, vol. 34, no. 6, 2019.
- [13] M. Colli et al., “A field assessment of a rain estimation system based on satellite-to-earth microwave links,” *IEEE Trans. on Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 57, no. 5, pp. 2864–2875, 2018.
- [14] F. Giannetti and R. Reggiannini, “Opportunistic rain rate estimation from measurements of satellite downlink attenuation: A survey,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 17, 2021.
- [15] F. Saggese, V. Lottici, and F. Giannetti, “Rainfall map from attenuation data fusion of satellite broadcast and commercial microwave links,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 18, 2022.
- [16] C. Gianoglio et al., “Rain discrimination with machine learning classifiers for opportunistic rain detection system using satellite micro-wave links,” *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 3, 2023.
- [17] A. Overeem, H. Leijnse, and R. Uijlenhoet, “Retrieval algorithm for rainfall mapping from microwave links in a cellular communication network,” *Atmospheric Measurements Techniques*, vol. 9, pp. 2425–2444, 2016.
- [18] G. Cazzaniga et al., “Hydrological response of a peri-urban catchment exploiting conventional and unconventional rainfall observations: The case study of lambro catchment,” *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences Discussions*, vol. 2021, pp. 1–26, 2021.
- [19] M. Colli et al., “Rainfall fields monitoring based on satellite microwave down-links and traditional techniques in the city of genoa,” *IEEE Trans. on Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 58, no. 9, pp. 6266–6280, 2020.
- [20] C. Riva et al., “The alphasat aldo paraboni propagation experiment: measurement campaign at the italian ground stations,” *Int. J. Satell. Commun. Netw.*, vol. 37, no. 5, 2018.
- [21] F. Giannetti et al., “On the opportunistic use of commercial ku and ka band satcom networks for rain rate estimation: Potentials and critical issues,” in *ICASSP 2020 - 2020 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 9011–9015.
- [22] X. Shen et al., “3-d tomographic reconstruction of rain field using microwave signals from leo satellites: Principle and simulation results,” *IEEE Trans. on Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 57, no. 8, 2019.